

ISSUES OF URBAN PLANNING DEVELOPMENT

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Annotation . The article studies urban planning, where it considers complex multilateral activities for the creation, development and reconstruction of settlements, including architectural engineering design, as well as urban planning as the theory and practice of planning and development of cities in the modern period, with the restructuring of the management of the national economy, thereby studying in obtaining maximum effect in achieving the design goals of urban planning works.

Key words: Urban planning, creative activity, design, city construction, national norms, rules, instructions, design, planning, documentation.

Urban planning has always been a powerful means of creating architecture, the most advanced urban ensembles of the past and present, which is a value for the future generation.

Urban planning is a broad and diverse creative activity that unites and connects with the construction and reconstruction of cities, national economic planning, architectural and planning design, organization and production of construction work. "Urban planning" studies the most important issues of urban planning, in connection with which the city's master plan necessarily contains elements of forecasting and foreseeing the further development of the urban organism, thereby representing what cities should be like in the future, based on real prospects and its development.

Urban planning, like most complex multifaceted areas of activity, is a complex and extensive system of knowledge, which includes:

- *geography and sociology of cities;*
- *urban economics;*
- *city government;*
- *energy supply to cities;*
- *engineering preparation of territories and a number of other complexes.*

When considering the ways of development of modern urban planning, it is important to realize that the world in which we live has changed radically and continues to develop rapidly.

We can consider important trends in social development that influence the development of urban planning:

- *cultural;*
- *cultural and entertainment centers and complexes;*
- *theme amusement parks;*
- *culinary parks;*
- *exhibition centers;*
- *festival centers;*
- *shopping and service centers and complexes;*
- *medical and recreational,*
- *sports and entertainment,*
- *tourist centers and complexes*
- *and a number of other developments of public spaces.*

Urban planning policy should be formed with the active participation of the population, in which the development of urban planning projects (design and planning documentation) that determine the prospects for the development of settlements and ensure the effective use of territorial and urban planning resources, optimization of development processes, and compliance with urban planning discipline.

Construction is carried out on the basis of a pre-developed project and planning of the city master plan. Urban planning has a great influence on the development of society, being the largest in the real economy, which concentrates a large material resource of buildings and structures, land plots that influence the processes of socio-economic development. Each urban planning system has the corresponding qualities of its constituent elements, which are determined by the complex interrelations between the elements of the urban planning system.

Urban planning shapes the appearance of our world and the ongoing changes cannot be reflected in them; it is the development of urban planning projects (design and planning documentation) that determine the prospects for the development of settlements and ensure the effective use of territorial and urban planning resources, optimization of development processes and adherence to urban planning discipline.

An urban planning project is an urban planning document that determines the directions and conditions for urban development of populated areas and between the rural population of territories. The urban planning project serves as the basis for projects at the following design levels and the basis for the implementation of specialized and sectoral schemes and projects.

The main types of urban development projects are:

- *master plan;*
- *detailed;*
- *specialized plans.*

The master plan is the main urban planning document developed on the territory of cities, other settlements, individual urban planning and territorial entities.

A detailed plan is a legal document that determines the nature of the use of the boundaries of territories, their individual parts and sections according to their functional purpose.

A specialized plan is a document defining an urban planning solution to individual problems of populated areas.

In their work, social designers today implement two main procedures:

Firstly, when designing, they are planning a new object, a new quality of social life.

Secondly, the development of a planned object takes place, where the consideration and coordination of the requirements for the structural tasks of the main elements and connections between objects are considered.

Thus, when forming modern strategies, social engineering actions, a peculiar distribution of the design itself occurs, where potential users are modeled and all this presupposes self-determination of social design, since in the general design scheme, each specific type of production specialization of the territory must correspond to its own type of distributed structure, and also provide the entire population with urban planning design documentation as a basis for making effective informed urban planning decisions and thereby create a reliable, reliable and accessible database of urban planning information for all participants in urban planning.

For the design of cities, national norms, rules and instructions strictly establish the procedure and stages of design work, providing for the types of urban planning documentation for the planning organization of the territory, planning and development of cities. In some special cases, city construction and development projects can be drawn up in parallel with the development of a master plan, where the content of the design task is different for different stages and types of urban planning work. In urban planning, the design of a building for the preparation of detailed planning projects must necessarily clarify the nature of the objects located within the boundaries of the red lines, the designed area,

as well as the requirements for landscaping, engineering equipment and engineering preparation of the area's territory.

Consolidated urban planning schemes for the territories of several subjects define:

- *zoning of territories;*
- *measures to develop regional settlement systems;*
- *measures to develop engineering, transport and social infrastructures;*
- *measures for rational use of natural resources and provision of resources for the purpose of integrated development of regions;*
- *sphere of mutual interests and municipalities in the field of urban planning.*

In addition to the mandatory provisions, the master plan of a settlement, urban district may contain provisions on urban planning zoning of territories, which determine the approximate boundaries of territorial zones, generalized types of their functional use, taking into account urban planning restrictions, as well as the recommended sequence of project development, planning of various territorial units of the settlement, urban district with for the purpose of establishing lines of urban planning regulation.

The master plan reveals the planning framework of the territory, as a result of the combination of different functional contents:

- *natural-ecological;*
- *cultural and historical;*
- *functional and planning;*
- *transport and communication and a number of other compositions.*

The criteria for evaluating options for urban planning design solutions are the following characteristics:

- *architectural and artistic;*
- *planning;*
- *sanitary and hygienic;*
- *technology – economic indicators.*

Comparison of assessment options is carried out in two ways by comparing the system and indicators, quantitative and qualitative, i.e. (objective and subjective). where the design standards for urban development facilities are mandatory when performing all types of design work and are approved by the relevant organizations.

At the design stage, a project is a set of technical documents that fully characterize what is planned for the construction of any complexes. The design

assignment contains the necessary data on the purpose and capacity of the area being designed, the relevant building codes and regulations, which constitute the urban design program.

During the design process, several options can be developed, the main ones being mathematical methods, computer technology and programming, in addition to the introduction in practice of automated systems in urban planning of cities, which allows for a multi-aspect search for the most rational solution to problems.

The importance of urban planning as the theory and practice of planning and development of cities is increasing in the modern period, when, with the restructuring of the management of the national economy, the improvement of its economic mechanisms, and the democratization of social processes, an increasing role in planning the development of cities is given to local governments, local economic structures, physical and legal persons.

In the new conditions, there is an increasing need to universalize the training of specialists with the necessary knowledge in the field of urban planning, who will have to carry out design, planning and research types of professional activity. This will require deepening general theoretical urban planning knowledge, understanding the patterns of urban development and settlement, acquiring skills in conducting sociological and environmental research, and assessing the impact of land use forms and land values on territorial planning decisions.

Modern urban planning represents the theory and practice of settlement in all its forms and at all levels of systems: **at the highest** - the country as a whole, large regions, **at the middle** - a region, region, intra-regional industrial or agricultural area, **lower levels** - city, town, village.

All these levels of spatial organization are interconnected, and when designing, strict continuity in the transition from one level to another must be observed, which is achieved in the process of social, economic and environmental forecasting and urban planning. Currently, in our country, as a result of many years of development, a fairly clear multi-level system of scientific and design work in urban planning has been formed, within the framework of which constructive settlement problems are solved. The top level is occupied by works of national and regional significance. As part of these works, a general scheme of settlement in the country and consolidated urban planning schemes are being carried out. At the middle level, territorial comprehensive urban planning schemes for the development of cities and districts are being developed.

where are defined:

- *zones of various functional purposes and restrictions on the use of territories;*
- *measures to protect territories from the impact of natural and man-made emergencies;*
- *directions for the development of inter-settlement infrastructures;*
- *reserve territories and territories for individual housing construction, territories for organizing recreational areas for the population.*

To carry out urban planning forecasting, along with traditional disciplines such as economics, planning, engineering, architecture, sociology, demography, political science, management, marketing, ecology and a number of other areas must also be involved.

Urban planning zoning is the zoning of municipal territories in order to determine territorial zones and establish urban planning regulations. Territorial zones are zones for which the land use and development rules define boundaries and establish town planning regulations.

Example: urban zoning maps - this urban zoning is the process and result of dividing territories within the boundaries of a municipality depending on their functional use into zones, for each of which an urban planning regulation is determined, establishing the types and parameters of the permitted urban use of land plots and capital construction projects within the territorial zone.

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